

Groove Gap Waveguide in 3-D Printed Technology for Low Loss, Weight, and Cost Distribution Networks

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Abstract—This paper presents the design and fabrication of low loss, weight, and cost prototypes in groove gap waveguide technology at Ka-band, manufactured with a metallized 3-D printing technique. A wide analysis of loss mechanisms and printing imperfections has been conducted, as well as the effect of temperature on structural deformations. Metallized 3-D printed and CNC machined prototypes have been compared and characterized with simulations and measurements at a band from 28 to 30 GHz. The average measured losses for metallized plastic prototypes are 1.4 dB/m.

Index Terms—Additive manufacturing, distribution network, groove gap waveguide (GGW), Ka-band, low cost, low loss, low weight, low-profile antenna, metallized 3-D printed technology, milling, roughness, thermal.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE arrival of new communication services at frequencies above Ka-band demands feasible solutions for mass developing of antenna systems. This implies challenges in both technology and manufacturing processes. Common technologies like PCB or rectangular waveguides (RWs) have been used during decades for the design and manufacturing of antenna systems, but they present opposed advantages and disadvantages at high frequencies [1]. On the one hand, manufacturing costs for PCB are reduced due to its simplicity and it presents a low weight, but the insertion losses at Ka-band and above are high due to the presence of a dielectric substrate and to the geometry of the conductor, which tends to be physically smaller than in RW. On the other hand, RW provides very low losses, but its integration on a complex planar structure with a good performance is difficult and expensive. An easy manufacturing way is building the structures in two parts, but bad electrical contacts due to roughness or nonuniform surfaces degrade the behavior and the resulting designs are

Fig. 1. Example of the structure for GGW.

heavy. Recently, gap waveguide (GW) technology [2] has been proposed in order to achieve very low losses while keeping a good manufacturing performance. GW is based on the use of a periodic structure of metallic pins that generates a high-impedance surface above those pins. When a metal plate is placed above the pins at a distance smaller than a quarter-wavelength, fields cannot propagate through this structure in a certain frequency band. Groove GW (GGW) [3] uses a rectangular path surrounded by the pin lattice, as shown in Fig. 1, that behaves like an RW and a quasi-TE₁₀ mode propagates. In this paper, the designed prototype is based on the GGW technology manufactured with a metallized 3-D printing process.

For planar structures, GGW is preferred over RW because a good electric contact is not necessary and the distribution network can easily be built in two parts without leakage losses. There are many works in the literature that exploit the contactless characteristic of GGW with sawing and milling techniques in metallic materials [4], [5], but these techniques suppose several disadvantages. The most important are the weight of the structures and the manufacturing time that the mechanizing process of the metal takes. This fact also increases notably the cost for the periodic structures. New generation antennas need to solve these problems in order to make a massive deployment feasible. The rise of 3-D printing and continuous development of the necessary technology have boosted the manufacture of various professional designs for both prototyping and mass production. Stimulation of this technology has had a major impact on many sectors of industry, including the field of radio communications and antenna design [6]. Several designs and applications of 3-D printed parts have been reported during last years with intricate electronic structures [7] or for low cost substrate integrated components for microwave frequencies [8]–[11]. For a complete adaptation of 3-D printed plastic technology in antenna field, an accurate printing result and metallization of the printed pieces are essential, with a low roughness

Fig. 2. (a) 3-D view of the GGW structure. (b) Cross section.

TABLE I
PARAMETERS OF GGW BASE STRUCTURE

Parameter	Length (mm)	Parameter	Length (mm)
h	0.6	p	2.6
D	1	d	3
W	8	Materials	Aluminium/Copper

coating metal. Together with 3-D printing, technology for metallizing models in various plastic materials has been developed. This provides great advantages over existing metal machining technology, which are: ease of manufacture, reduced costs, reduced lead times, reduced weight, and increase in RF design flexibility. Recently, several works have presented metallized 3-D printed designs at high frequencies with very good results [12], [13].

The main objective of this paper is to analyze the constraints that metallized 3-D printing technology imposes over GGW designs for distribution networks in planar structures and compare the performance with common milling techniques in aluminum. The organization of this paper is as follows. Section II shows the designs and simulations of transitions to WR-28, bends, and power dividers in the selected technology. Section III presents the properties of the metallized 3-D printing technology that has been used, together with a comparison with common milling aluminum techniques. A parametric study of the effect of different physical properties such as roughness or manufacturing imperfections is conducted in Section IV. Section V exposes a comparison of simulations and measurements of the final manufactured prototypes and a study of losses per unit length in metallized 3-D printed GGW. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section VI.

II. GGW DESIGN FOR A BAND FROM 28 TO 30 GHz

A. Base Groove Gap Waveguide Structure

The base structure includes a bed of nails made of three rows of pins for the lateral lattice in a copper plated surface that is covered by an aluminum plate. A 3-D view of this structure is shown in Fig. 2(a), a cross section in Fig. 2(b), and the design parameters are provided in Table I.

Fig. 3 represents the dispersion diagram of the structure. This diagram has been calculated using the Eigenmode Solver in CST considering a unit cell with periodic boundaries in the direction of propagation. The desired band for our application includes frequencies from 28 to 30 GHz.

The start and end frequencies of the single mode band are 23.02 and 39.53 GHz, respectively. As it can be seen, this single mode band includes the desired frequency band. In Fig. 3, the first six modes are degenerated TE modes that

Fig. 3. Dispersion diagram of the unit cell. Mode TE₁₀ through groove is the mode of interest.

propagate within the pins below the stopband of the bed of nails. The mode of interest quasi-TE₁₀ propagates only through the groove, with an insignificant amount of radiated field outside the bed of nails [see Fig. 19(b)]. The last two modes represented are degenerated quasi-TE₂₀ and quasi-TM₁₁ modes in the groove whose fields considerably extend beyond the pin lattice.

B. Design of a 90° Bend, a Power Divider, a Transition to WR-28, and a TRL Calibration Kit in GGW

The design in GGW is very limited by the diameter of the pins (D) and the separation between them (p), which should be at least 1 and 2 mm, respectively, to ensure a correct metallization of the plastic model. Different elements that may be present in a distribution network have been designed, such as a 90° bend, a two-way power divider and a transition between GGW and WR-28. The design and optimization of all the elements consist of setting several pins in the adequate positions. In the case of the 90° bend, only one pin has been optimized [Fig. 4(a)], whereas the structures for the power divider and the WR-28 transition are more complex. The design of the power divider is based on the proposed method found at [14] for an H -plane power divider in RW. The design consists of a septum divider and an iris at the input of the divider that narrows the width of the GGW. These two structures have been implemented with pins [Fig. 4(b)]. In relation to the WR-28 to GGW transition, a structure similar to that found in [4] is used; with the input slot in the bottom plate of the GGW model. In the optimization, we have also taken into account the screws from bottom to top metal plates for joining the WR-28 flange with the GGW model [Fig. 4(c)].

The S-parameters of the simulated results for the three structures are depicted in Fig. 5. The insertion losses vary from 0.01 to 0.05 dB in the desired band for the three cases. However, reflection coefficient is much better in the 90° bend than in the other two structures, with a value lower than -40 dB between 28 and 30 GHz and a fractional bandwidth at -20 dB close to 30%. The fractional bandwidth at -20 dB

Fig. 4. (a) Bend structure. (b) Power divider structure. (c) WR-28 to GGW transition structure. Optimized values in millimeters.

Fig. 5. Simulated S-parameters for the optimized bend, the two-way power divider, and the WR-28 to GGW transition. The S_{21} parameter for the power divider is represented adding 3 dB to the simulated values.

for the power divider and the transition to WR-28 is reduced to 14% and 10%, respectively. We consider these results acceptable for our application.

The effect of the transitions between GGW and WR-28 can be important in the estimation of the properties of the technology itself. Because of that, we have designed a TRL calibration kit that allows measurements removing the effect of these transitions. The TRL kit consists of the structures in Fig. 6, which include thru, reflect, and two lines with different lengths.

III. METALLIZED PLASTIC VERSUS MACHINED ALUMINIUM

For the interests of this paper, metallized 3-D printing is oriented to the design of structures using air as substrate material. GW is the suitable technology for manufacturing in

Fig. 6. TRL calibration kit for our GGW structure.

Fig. 7. Prototype in machined (a) aluminum and (b) metallized 3-D.

TABLE II
PROPERTIES OF COPPER PLATING, PLASTIC, AND ALUMINIUM

Parameter	Copper plating	Plastic	Aluminium
Material	99.9% pure copper	Accura [®] SL 5530	AL-6082-T6 95% Al min.
Mass density	8.96 g/cm ³	1.25 g/cm ³	2.71 g/cm ³
Electric cond.	$5.8 \cdot 10^7$ S/m	~	$2.55 \cdot 10^7$ S/m
Thermal cond.	401 W/mK	0.173 W/mK	172 W/mK
Coeff. thermal expansion	$16.6 \cdot 10^{-6}/K$	$84 \cdot 10^{-6}/K$ (T<122 °C) $159 \cdot 10^{-6}/K$ (T>122 °C)	$23.1 \cdot 10^{-6}/K$
Fusion/deflect. temperature	1,084 °C	210 °C (0.455 N/mm ²) 115 °C (1.82 N/mm ²)	610 °C

metallized 3-D printed plastic, because an electrical connection between upper and lower metallic plates is not needed. This allows us to manufacture the two parts separately. The critical part is the one that includes the periodic lateral pins, which presents a periodic structure that can be printed and metallized very easily. The design of GGW models has been implemented in 3-D printed technology plated with a 10- μ m copper layer obtained after an electrolytic process. The parts are built using a 3-D Systems viper stereolithographic (SLA) printer and the accuracy of the final printed structure is specified as 50 μ m in the horizontal plane and 100 μ m in the vertical direction due to the stacking of plastic layers.

We have manufactured two prototypes in GGW technology: one using milling aluminum technique and the other one with metallized 3-D printing to conduct a realistic comparison between both manufacturing methods. The results of a single straight section both in metallized plastic and in machined aluminum are presented in Fig. 7. A comparison between the properties of materials and technologies can be found in Table II.

The more relevant advantages of metallized 3-D printed plastic in comparison to common machined aluminum technique for the prototypes in Fig. 7 are presented next. The plated plastic model achieves a weight reduction of 48% of the

Fig. 8. SEM images of a pin in (a) aluminum and (b) copper plated plastic. Optical microscope images of the corner of the transition in (c) aluminum and (d) copper plated plastic. In (b), the stacked layers can be observed in the top of the pin. A worse manufacturing result of the transition is observed in (c) than in (d) due to the diameter of the milling drill.

weight in machined model. The total cost of the 3-D printed prototype is 16% of the cost for the machined model. This cost depends on the manufacturing time, which is 30 min for the 3-D printed model. However, our design is optimized for 3-D printing and mechanizing time may be reduced considering squared pins homogeneously distributed. This would reduce degrees of freedom in the design process, but it supposes a reduction of 20% in machining time and cost.

Apart from these remarkable advantages, both techniques present manufacturing drawbacks. On the one hand, the flat and wide structure of the plastic piece has forced to build the part at angle in order to avoid curved surfaces due to material shrink. This transfers the accuracy in vertical direction ($100\ \mu\text{m}$) of the stacked layers along all surfaces and print lines become visible, as it can be observed in Fig. 8(b). On the other hand, with an accuracy of $10\ \mu\text{m}$, the aluminum prototype does not present this problem. Nevertheless, there are limitations at the corners in WR-28 transitions due to the 0.5-mm radius of the milling cutter [Fig. 8(c)].

A study of the surface profile in both prototypes has been performed to observe the limiting imperfections. In Fig. 9, scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of the roughness are presented in both cases. For a better estimation of the roughness, we include measurements with profilometer in Fig. 10, whose results are coherent with the visual aspect shown in Fig. 9. An additional measurement of the waviness in the plastic model reveals the stacking of layers and the printing angle in Fig. 11.

In Fig. 12, the detailed structure of transitions for both technologies is shown for the prototypes in Fig. 7. The stacked layers in the printed prototype can be appreciated in Fig. 12(a). In the case of the aluminum prototype in Fig. 12(b), the rounded corners are visible, as well as a certain roughness of

Fig. 9. SEM micrographs of the surface roughness in aluminum with (a) x1500 amplification factor and (b) x7000 in copper plated plastic.

Fig. 10. Measurements and normal distribution fitting of the surface roughness obtained with the profilometer Veeco DekTak 150. Measured roughness (DIN EN ISO 4287) in the copper surface (a) is $R_q = 0.3\ \mu\text{m}$. The value obtained for the aluminium surface (b) corresponds to $R_q = 3.5\ \mu\text{m}$. The practical resolution in vertical direction is better than 10 nm.

Fig. 11. (a) Waviness of the copper surfaces due to the stacked layers of the plastic during the 3-D printing process. (b) Detailed view of a single layer with a thickness of $100\ \mu\text{m}$ and an elevation angle of 15° . Apart from the tilt in elevation, the layers are also disposed with an angle of 45° in azimuth with respect to the direction of propagation [see Fig. 12(a)].

the material due to a sanding process applied after fabrication. We have simulated both models considering the roundness and the stacking of layers, together with the roughness measured in Fig. 10. The simulated and measured results of the models presented in Fig. 7 are compared in Fig. 13.

As it can be seen in Fig. 13(a), the main difference is in the insertion losses, being significantly higher in the machined model due to the roughness level. In general terms, simulation

Fig. 12. (a) Detailed structure of metallized and (b) machined models. A caption of the simulated structure is placed at the (a) top-right corner and (b) top-left corner.

Fig. 13. Comparison of measurement (MEAS) and simulation (SIM) for the metallized 3-D printed plastic (3-D) and the machined (MC) models. (a) Amplitude of S-parameters and (b) S_{21} phase difference between 3-D and MC. Prototypes have been measured with an Agilent 8722ES Network Analyzer after a TRL calibration with an HP R11644A WR-28 Calibration Kit.

and measurement are in very good agreement, especially for the 3-D printed model. Simulated reflection coefficient slightly differs from the measurement in the machined model due to manufacturing deviations. The average losses between 28 to 30 GHz are shown in Table III for the simulations and measurements presented in Fig. 13(a), together with the losses considering ideal properties of the materials. Ideal simulations do not consider roughness or manufacturing imperfections. The roughness found in the machined device stems from a sanding process applied after the milling of the material. This additional process removes the burrs and undesired edges in the piece. Regarding the phase delay due to roughness, phase difference between 3-D printed model and machined model is depicted in Fig. 13(b) with a phase difference of 3° at 29 GHz approximately. Additional comparisons between

TABLE III
LOSSES IN METALLIZED 3-D PRINTED PLASTIC AND MACHINED TECHNOLOGIES

Model	Losses (dB)	Model	Losses (dB)
3D Ideal	0.056	MC Ideal	0.073
3D Simulation	0.085	MC Simulation	0.326
3D Measurement	0.088	MC Measurement	0.315

Fig. 14. (a) Attenuation and (b) phase delay increment per unit length in the GGW structure in function of the roughness R_q of the copper surface. Losses increase approximately 1 dB/m for each additional $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ of roughness at 29 GHz. The increment in phase delay is not as lineal, being lower when increasing roughness.

simulations and measurements of several prototypes in metallized 3-D printed plastic are presented in Section V.

IV. PARAMETRIC STUDY AND GGW VERSUS RECTANGULAR WAVEGUIDE PERFORMANCE

In this section, several parametric studies have been conducted for different values of electrical and physical properties of the materials.

A. Modeling the Impact of Roughness and Conductivity

Due to the fact that the surface roughness supposes a greater impact over the losses than conductivity, losses and phase delay have been simulated for different values of roughness R_q in Fig. 14 and conductivity σ in Fig. 15. Roughness is modeled using the gradient model in CST MWS [13], considering the value of roughness R_q as the standard deviation of the surface profile. This effect increases surface impedance and introduces additional attenuation α [Fig. 14(a)] and a phase delay [Fig. 14(b)]. The reduction of the conductivity of the metal itself also increases the surface impedance, but to a lesser extent as it is shown in Fig. 15(a) and (b).

B. Modeling the Impact of Copper Thickness

As it can be seen in Fig. 16(a), skin depths from Ka-band to W-band are on the order of the measured roughness; so, it is expected that its effect on losses at 60 or 90 GHz will not be remarkable. As copper thickness is several multiples of the skin depth, practically no field escapes from the metallic layer [see Fig. 16(b)]. A thickness of $2.67 \mu\text{m}$, or seven multiples of the skin depth, is considered enough to avoid any important effect in the performance due to radiation through

Fig. 15. (a) Attenuation and (b) phase delay increment per unit length in the GGW structure in function of the conductivity σ of the surface. Losses and phase delay are inversely proportional to the square root of the conductivity. Comparing the results with the ones in Fig. 14, the main contribution of losses and phase delay come from surface roughness in the most typical cases.

Fig. 16. (a) Skin depth as a function of frequency and (b) amplitude decay for the skin depth at 30 GHz considering an ideally smooth conductor surface.

the copper plating. Furthermore, as it will be seen in Fig. 21, where even 100 μm of stacked layers do not suppose a great deviation in the S-parameters, the extra copper layer of several micrometers in all the surfaces during the fabrication process is negligible and it is not necessary to take into account in the design process.

C. Modeling the Impact of Bad Contacts in GGW and RW

Apart from conductor properties, the main advantage of GW technology over classical RW resides in the contactless surfaces. Manufacturing a planar structure in RW is very complex in both machined and plated-printed technologies in a single piece. For a fair comparison, both technologies have been compared and divided in two parts: the main structure in the lower copper plate and a covering upper aluminum plate. We have simulated both structures considering a bad electrical contact represented by a certain separation of the upper metal plate from its ideal position. This separation inserts a space of air of several micrometers. In Fig. 17, the effect in the losses for WR-28 and GGW is depicted for various separations. For WR-28, losses increase about 1 dB/m for each additional micrometer of separation, while in GGW are practically constant. Fig. 18 shows the leakage of fields in the WR-28, which does not occur in GGW. This behavior makes the GGW a better candidate than RW for integrated planar networks if losses are critical, despite the increase of volume due to the periodic pins.

Fig. 17. (a) Attenuation of WR-28. (b) GGW structure due to the bad contact sep between top and bottom plates, which is zero for the ideal case.

Fig. 18. (a) Field leakage of GGW. (b) WR-28. Cross section of the amplitude of the electric field at the bad contact for a separation of 1 μm . (a) is represented in Fig. 19(b) with an extended scale for a better visualization.

Fig. 19. (a) Attenuation due to radiation through the lateral pins in function of the number N_{pins} of periodic rows. (b) Cross section of the amplitude of electric field for the three rows case (our design). The difference between N_{pins} three or four is negligible, with an amplitude lower than -75 dB outside the structure.

D. Modeling the Impact of Field Leakage Through Pins

Since insertion losses measured in Fig. 13 are below 0.1 dB, the contribution of radiation through the periodic pins may be important. In Fig. 18(a), radiation losses are not visible due to the limited scale. Therefore, we include a study of radiation losses in function of the number of pin rows [Fig. 19(a)] and the level of simulated fields beyond the pins [Fig. 19(b)]. The results conclude that the optimum number of rows of pins is three, with a radiated field of about -80 dB in relation to the amplitude of the field at the center of the GGW. This means that the impact of radiation losses in measurements is negligible.

Fig. 20. Structure and configuration of the stacked layers. Layers are disposed with a tilt of 15° and an angle of 45° in respect of the direction of propagation. Simulated thicknesses δ_{layer} are (a) $100 \mu\text{m}$, (b) $200 \mu\text{m}$, and (c) $300 \mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 21. Deviation in S-parameters due to the thickness δ_{layer} of plastic layers. (a) Reflection coefficient. (b) Transmission coefficient.

E. Modeling the Impact of Stacked Layers of Plastic

Another aspect of the manufacturing process that may lead into important deviations in the final response of the prototypes is the thickness of the stacked layers of plastic. A parametric simulation has been conducted considering different values of thicknesses δ_{layer} shown in Fig. 20 for a 90-mm length model from input to output.

The results for reflection coefficient are shown in Fig. 21(a) and for transmission in Fig. 21(b). An important shift to lower frequencies is appreciated for larger thicknesses, but the difference between the ideal structure ($\delta_{\text{layer}} \rightarrow 0 \mu\text{m}$) and our manufactured structure ($\delta_{\text{layer}} = 100 \mu\text{m}$) is not of great relevance. However, this may be a problem when extending this technology at higher frequencies. Then, a better printing resolution will be required, but this does not represent a problem at least until 100 GHz because the manufacturing capacity can achieve a stacking of $50\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ layers or less.

F. Modeling the Impact of Mechanical Deformation With Temperature

For a complete analysis, a study of the effects over the EM response in function of temperature has been conducted. Thermal and mechanical properties of the materials are introduced in the simulation. First, a temperature simulation of the model considering thermal losses coming from EM calculation has been performed at a certain ambient temperature T . The result is used as an input for a mechanical simulation with

Fig. 22. (a) Material displacement of a solid copper model and (b) copper plated plastic at an ambient temperature of 100°C (Reference temperature = 25°C). Deformation in plastic is more pronounced because its coefficient of thermal expansion is higher. Transitions to WR-28 are fixed to the system and do not experiment any displacement.

Fig. 23. (a) Variation in S_{11} parameter and (b) S_{21} parameter in function of temperature.

a reference temperature. The generated deformation mesh is simulated again with the EM solver in order to obtain the deviation due to temperature deformations [16]. Fig. 22 represents the mechanical deformation in the bottom plate of the models in solid copper (a) and plated plastic (b) at 100°C and Fig. 23 depicts the simulated variations in S-parameters of such model for -50°C , 25°C , and 100°C . Results present a good behavior in a wide range of temperatures with minimal changes in the response.

Simulations have not been evaluated at higher temperatures because the deflection temperature of the plastic is about 115°C .

V. FINAL DESIGNS PROTOTYPE AND RESULTS

In this section, we present the final models that have been manufactured compared with the simulated results.

A. Simulations and Measurements for Straight Section, U-Shaped Section, and Two- and Four-Way Power Dividers

The models included in the prototype are a straight section, a U-shaped section with two bends in its structure, a two-way power divider and a four-way power divider. All of

Fig. 24. (b) 3-D printed plastic and (a) metallized GGW prototype. The 3-D printed prototype is covered with a drilled aluminum plate. (c) Top view of the prototype with aluminum plate. (d) Bottom view of the prototype and measuring set-up.

Fig. 25. (a) Straight section. (b) U-shaped section with two bends. (c) Two-way power divider. (d) Four-way power divider. These four parts have a total length from input to output WR-28 transitions of 90 mm.

them have been modeled with a total length from inputs to outputs of 90 mm. This allows us to check the differences between them in return and transmission losses. Photographs of the complete prototype are shown in Fig. 24 and a detailed view of the four basic parts needed for a distribution network in Fig. 25. The printing time for the complete piece was 12 h and 14 min.

A comparison of measurements and ideal simulations of the four prototypes shown in Fig. 25 are depicted in Fig. 26. We consider the behavior of the transition as a critical part of the system. Because of that, measurements presented in Fig. 26 have been made using the TRL calibration kit for WR-28 instead of the *ad hoc* TRL in Fig. 6. Thus, the effect of the transition is present in the results. Our designed TRL calibration kit has been used in Section VI for measuring a straight section to estimate the losses per unit length.

The obtained results in Fig. 26 reveal that measurements fit very well with simulations. The measured losses for straight section [Fig. 26(a)] and U-shaped section [Fig. 26(b)] are

TABLE IV
MEASURED BANDWIDTH AND AVERAGE LOSSES AT 28 TO 30 GHz

Prototype. 90 mm length	Fractional bandwidth		Average losses in 28-30 GHz band
	-10 dB	-20 dB	
Straight section	18.14 %	8.52 %	0.16 dB
U-shaped section	16.55 %	7.41 %	0.17 dB
Two-way power divider	16.10 %	4.72 %	0.22 dB
Four-way power divider	15.97 %	3.27 %	0.34 dB

approximately 0.15 dB in the desired band with a minimum ripple, which coincides with simulations. However, measured transmission parameters in the two-way power divider [Fig. 26(c)] and the four-way power divider [Fig. 26(d)] present a ripple of about 0.5 dB that does not appear in the ideal simulation. We consider that this is mainly caused by the use of WR-28 loads in the transitions that are not connected to the network analyzer, whose reflection parameter is very good but not enough for measuring levels of tenths of decibel. A measurement of the loads gave us a reflection coefficient less than -40 dB. Then, for a convenient comparison between simulation and measurement, we have done an additional simulation considering the -40 -dB reflection loads. The reflection level at the outputs can be configured in CST defining an open boundary in the output plane, whose reflectivity can be modified. The comparisons between measurement, ideal simulation, and simulation with imperfect loads are depicted in Fig. 26(c) and (d) for the two-way and four-way power divider, respectively. It can be observed that the ripple also appears in the new simulation with a variation of about 0.5 dB, as in the measurements.

In relation to reflection coefficient, measurements and simulations are in a good agreement with a value better than -20 dB between 28 and 30 GHz for the straight section and U-shaped section. Reflection level in power dividers at Fig. 26(c) and (d) is higher than in simulations, which indicates that it is produced by errors in manufacturing process. Those errors may be the stacked layers in the top of the pins at the septum divider, which also may contribute to the ripple in S_{21} .

In general, the obtained results validate the good performance of our manufacturing technology. Manufacturing imperfections may be responsible of the slightly displacement in frequency that can be observed.

In summary, we present a comparison of average losses in the frequency band from 28 to 30 GHz and values for fractional bandwidth at -10 and -20 dB in Table IV.

We observe that bandwidth is degraded for the measurements in the U-shaped section and power dividers compared with the straight section. The bandwidth is even more degraded for the power dividers at -20 -dB reflection level because of the relatively narrowband of the designed power divider shown in Fig. 4(b). The reflection level of the dividing structure is close to the level of the transitions to WR-28, so the combined contribution increases the reflection and reduces the bandwidth. The bandwidth for the straight sections and the U-shaped section are very similar, with slightly deviations in the position of maximums of reflection due to the presence of the bends. Losses are very close to the simulations and

Fig. 26. Measurement and simulation of the prototypes in Fig. 25. S_{11} and S_{21} parameters of the straight section and the U-shaped section are shown in (a) and (b), respectively, being the curves for the simulated results indicated with “Ideal” and the measured curves with “Meas” in the legend. Results for the two and four-way power dividers are depicted in (c) and (d). Both graphics include curves “Loads” with simulations of the power dividers considering that there are imperfectly matched loads with a reflection level of -40 dB in the nonconnected ports during measurements. Simulations with perfectly matched loads are indicated with “Ideal.” The reason of that is to simulate a better approximation of the measurement procedure, as it is explained in the text below. In (c) and (d), we show the power imbalance between opposite ports 2 and 3 and ports 2 and 5 in the two and four-way power dividers, respectively [see Fig. 25(c) and (d)]. Prototypes have been measured with an Agilent 8722ES Network Analyzer after a TRL calibration with a HP R11644A WR-28 Calibration Kit.

Fig. 27. Straight section after TRL calibration. Comparison between calibrated simulations and measurements.

their levels are in line with the simulated losses for the single designed bend and divider.

B. Estimation of the Attenuation Constant α for the Metallized 3-D Printed GGW

The result for the straight section in Fig. 25(a) after calibrating with the TRL kit in Fig. 6 is shown in Fig. 27. Measured insertion losses and return losses are 0.1 and 20 dB,

TABLE V
AVERAGE ATTENUATION CONSTANT α

Model	α (dB/m)	Model	α (dB/m)
GGW Ideal Sim.	0.916	GGW Rough Sim.	1.357
WR-28 R896D Meas.	2.29	GGW Measurement	1.4

respectively, for a length of 70.2 mm. This allows the estimation of the attenuation constant α in this technology. Table V presents the result, together with ideal and realistic simulation of the GGW model and measured losses for a WR-28 section. The attenuation constant for WR-28 in Table V is measured for a 100-mm WR-28 standard section R896D, included in the HP R11644A WR-28 Calibration Kit. It is important to note that the measured value of 2.29 dB/m differs considerably from the theoretical value of 0.635 dB/m for an ideal WR-28 built in copper. Furthermore, attenuation constant is expected to increase if RW is implemented as an integrated planar structure with imperfect electric connections as it is shown in Figs. 17 and 18. Therefore, an attenuation of 1.4 dB/m in our GGW prototypes is a very good result.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper shows that it is possible to obtain low-cost designs for high frequencies distribution networks with

metallized 3-D printing technology without sacrificing a good performance. Copper plated plastic combines the good electrical conductivity of the copper and the low mass density of the plastic material. This allows obtaining a manufactured piece with lower weight and better conductivity than in machined aluminum. In addition, the reduced manufacturing times using 3-D printing suppose an advantage for prototyping. However, plastic presents a relatively low deflection temperature and a considerably different coefficient of thermal expansion compared to copper or aluminum. Because of that, this technology is well suited for terrestrial environments, but manufacturing with this kind of plastics is not recommended for spatial applications. Nevertheless, other plastic polymers with a high thermal stability may be used for that end. A deep analysis of the manufacturing technology has been conducted, compared with conventional milling techniques. The study of the effect of several physical properties highlights that roughness takes a fundamental role in losses at high frequencies. The importance of achieving good electrical contacts in rectangular waveguide makes the GGW a suitable alternative. Several prototypes in GGW technology have been designed and manufactured in metallized 3-D printed technology. The measured results strongly agree with simulations, presenting a bandwidth better than 15% at -10 dB centered at 29 GHz. The losses per unit length in this technology have been calculated using a TRL calibration kit and they are very close to the losses in a typical rectangular waveguide with an average value of 1.4 dB/m between 28 and 30 GHz, but with a fraction of the weight and cost.

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REFERENCES

- [1] D. M. Pozar, *Microwave Engineering*, 4th ed. New York, NY, USA: Wiley, 2011.
- [2] P.-S. Kildal, "Three metamaterial-based gap waveguides between parallel metal plates for mm/submm waves," in *Proc. 3rd Eur. Conf. Antennas Propag. (EuCAP)*, 2009, pp. 28–38.
- [3] A. Berenguer, V. Fusco, D. E. Zelenchuk, D. Sánchez-Escuderos, M. Baquero-Escudero, and V. E. Boria-Esbert, "Propagation characteristics of groove gap waveguide below and above cutoff," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 64, no. 1, pp. 27–36, Jan. 2016.
- [4] M. Rezaee, A. U. Zaman, and P.-S. Kildal, "V-band groove gap waveguide diplexer," in *Proc. 9th Eur. Conf. Antennas Propag. (EuCAP)*, Apr. 2015, pp. 1–4.
- [5] E. Alfonso, M. Baquero, P.-S. Kildal, A. Valero-Nogueira, E. Rajo-Iglesias, and J. I. Herranz, "Design of microwave circuits in ridge-gap waveguide technology," in *IEEE MTT-S Int. Microw. Symp. Dig.*, May 2010, pp. 1544–1547.
- [6] W. J. Otter and S. Lucyszyn, "3-D printing of microwave components for 21st century applications," in *Proc. IEEE MTT-S Int. Microw. Workshop Ser. Adv. Mater. Process. RF THz Appl. (IMWS-AMP)*, Jul. 2016, pp. 1–3.
- [7] E. Macdonald *et al.*, "3D printing for the rapid prototyping of structural electronics," *IEEE Access*, vol. 2, pp. 234–242, 2014.
- [8] S. Moscato *et al.*, "Additive manufacturing of 3D substrate integrated waveguide components," *Electron. Lett.*, vol. 51, no. 18, pp. 1426–1428, 2015.

- [9] S. Moscato *et al.*, "Exploiting 3D printed substrate for microfluidic SIW sensor," in *Proc. 45th Eur. Microw. Conf. (EuMC)*, Sep. 2015, pp. 28–31.
- [10] T. P. Ketterl *et al.*, "A 2.45 GHz phased array antenna unit cell fabricated using 3-D multi direct digital manufacturing," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 63, no. 12, pp. 4382–4394, Dec. 2015.
- [11] K. H. Church *et al.*, "Multimaterial and multilayer direct digital manufacturing of 3-D structural microwave electronics," *Proc. IEEE*, vol. 105, no. 4, pp. 688–701, Apr. 2017.
- [12] A. I. Dimitriadis, M. Favre, M. Billod, J.-P. Ansermet, and E. de Rijck, "Design and fabrication of a lightweight additive-manufactured Ka-band horn antenna array," in *Proc. 10th Eur. Conf. Antennas Propag. (EuCAP)*, Apr. 2016, pp. 1–4.
- [13] C. Guo, X. Shang, J. Li, M. J. Lancaster, and J. Xu, "3-D printed lightweight microwave waveguide devices," in *Proc. 5th Asia-Pacific Conf. Antennas Propag. (APCAP)*, Jul. 2016, pp. 47–48.
- [14] J.-H. Bang, S.-M. Hwang, S.-G. Lee, and B.-C. Ahn, "Design formulas for the H-plane septum power divider in a rectangular waveguide," *Microw. Opt. Technol. Lett.*, vol. 37, no. 5, pp. 390–393, 2003.
- [15] G. Gold, "Modeling surface roughness in CST microwave studio," in *Proc. 14th IEEE/IFIP Int. Conf. Embedded Ubiquitous Comput. (EUC)*, Apr. 2016, pp. 1–17.
- [16] U. Becker, "Multi-physics simulation with CST STUDIO SUITE," in *Proc. 10th IEEE/IFIP Int. Conf. Embedded Ubiquitous Comput. (EUC)*, Feb. 2012, pp. 1–19.

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